

Selection for other characters like plant height and tiller number per plant was not possible during rapid generation advance because of the narrow range within which varieties were distributed. Selection for suitable morphological char-

acters is only possible in the saline swamp in subsequent generations (F₆-F₇), where selection should be easier because only nearly fixed lines would be available. The range of various characters of F₆ plants (see table) grown in the field showed that

the variability was not lost over several generations of selfing in the rapid generation process. Rapid generation speeded the cycle without affecting individual plant potential for other morphological characters. □

Evaluation of some elite rice cultures for intercropping on Oxisols in coconut gardens

K. R. Vijayakumar, P. N. Unni, and V. K. Vamadevan, Water Management Agricultural Division, Centre for Water Resources Development and Management, Calicut 673571, India

Most coconut gardens in Kerala are planted on sloping terrain on Oxisols. Because 85% of the gardens are rainfed, coconut and long-duration perennial intercrops such as banana, cassava, and pineapple suffer severe moisture stress from Dec to May. Planting short-duration crops like upland rice during the monsoon (Jun-Nov) may reduce competition between coconut and intercrops for soil moisture. Upland rice cultivation in the rainfed coconut gardens could be lucrative, with suitable varieties and management practices.

Seven rice cultivars from the Central Rice Research Institute and one local cultivar (see table) were grown in a randomized block design in a coconut

Yield data of upland rice intercropped with coconut. 1980 kharif.^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains/panicle (no.)	1,000-grain wt (g)	Sterility (%)	Harvest index	Duration (d)
CR143-2-2	4.5	205	79	27	22	0.98	103
MW10	4.5	212	79	27	12	0.97	103
CR16 2-2	3.4	196	73	24	12	1.28	96
AUS61	4.2	114	184	20	15	0.59	109
BG35-2	3.7	181	63	31	43	0.62	109
CtG1516	4.2	186	94	24	9	0.94	96
ARC7001	3.7	204	61	26	27	0.69	96
Local check	2.1	218	37	29	25	0.55	99
LSD (0.05)	967.5	NS	18.8	1.9	1.9	15.14	0.05

^a Sowing date = 6 Sep 1980. Spacing = 20 × 10 cm. Plot size (harvested) = 3.4 × 1.6 m. Soil pH was 5.5 (0-30 cm depth). Rainfall in Jun, Jul, Aug, and Sep 1980 was 1369, 1325, 611, and 115 mm. Normal rainfall is 944, 1117, 599, and 262 mm.

garden with 40-year-old palms spaced 8 × 8 m at Kottamparamba (11° 15'N, 75° 52' E, altitude 80 m above sea level) 1980 monsoon. Plot size was 4 × 2 m. Farmyard manure at 5,000 kg/ha, lime at 250, N at 40, P at 20, and K at 20 were applied. NPK was applied in equal splits 15 and 30 d after sowing, both applications in combination with hand weeding. Bunds were opened to minimize standing

water. Appropriate insect controls were used. Rice was harvested in Sep.

CR143-2-2, MW10, AUS61, and CtG 1516 yielded more than 4 t/ha (see table), twice that of the local check. Although the data are for 1 year only, the study indicates the wide scope for adopting suitable rice varieties for intercropping in coconut-based cropping systems. □

Performance of rice varieties in sodic soils

K. N. Singh and D. K. Sharma, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, India

We assessed tolerance levels of varieties P2-21, Jaya, IR8, and CSR1 to highly sodic soils at Gudda Research Farm and to semireclaimed sodic soils at Karnal in 1982 kharif. Soil at Gudda was a sandy loam with pH 10.5, 92% exchangeable sodium, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.4 meq/100 g, 0.23% organic carbon, and cation exchange capacity 9.0 meq/100 g. Soil at Karnal was a sandy loam, with pH 8.7, 10% exchangeable sodium, exchangeable Ca + Mg 7.50 meq/100 g, 1.30% CaCO₃,

Relative performance of rice varieties in sodic and semireclaimed sodic soil.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (m)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (m)	pH after rice harvest ^a		% reduction of grain yield
					0-15 cm	15-30 cm	
<i>Semireclaimed sodic soil^a in Karnal</i>							
Jaya	7.2	92.7	9.6	21.3	8.5	8.8	—
IR8	7.5	98.8	9.8	21.1	8.5	8.7	—
P2-21	6.4	87.6	9.6	20.3	8.6	8.8	—
CSR1	4.5	136.6	9.5	19.4	8.5	8.7	—
CD (P = 0.05)	0.4	3.6	NS	1.5			
<i>Sodic soil at Gudda</i>							
Jaya	0.8	56.4	7.5	15.4	10.2	10.3	89
IR8	0.7	57.2	7.6	15.5	10.2	10.2	90
P2-21	0.8	64.5	7.4	15.6	10.1	10.3	87
CSR1	1.7	90.4	10.4	15.6	10.1	10.2	66
CD (P = 0.05)	0.04	4.8	1.3	NS	—	—	—

^a Initial pH (0-15 cm) was 8.7 for semireclaimed sodic soil and 10.5 for sodic soil.

and cation exchange capacity 10.0 meq/100 g.

Rice was transplanted 14 Jul. Soils had adequate available P and K, but all varieties received 150 kg N/ha as urea in 3 equal splits (at transplanting and at 25 and 50 d after transplanting) and 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha at transplanting. The experiment had four replications.

In Karnal, P2-21 was harvested 1 Oct, Jaya and IR8 were harvested 26 Oct, and CSRI was harvested 11 Nov. Sodic soil at Gudda delayed maturity and the same varieties were harvested on 14 Oct and 10 and 18 Nov.

Yields of Jaya and IR8 were similar at Karnal, and were significantly more than that of P2-21, which yielded significantly

more than CSRI (see table). On sodic soil, however, Jaya, IR8, and P2-21 yielded similarly and were significantly inferior to CSRI.

All varieties yielded much less in sodic soils than in semireclaimed sodic soil. The mean pH of the sodic soil decreased from 10.5 to 10.2 because of rice cultivation. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Yield characters for cold-tolerant rice

V. S. Chauhan, scientist, and J. P. Tandon, director, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture (VLHA), Almora, Uttar Pradesh, India

We studied yield-related characters for cold-tolerant rice at the VLHA, 1,300 m above sea level. Each of 380 entries included in the third International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery was transplanted at 20-cm spacing in nonreplicated plots in three 3-m-long rows.

Some cultures suffered severe post-anthesis cold damage, and only 225 entries were observed for yield. Plant height, tillers/plant, panicles/plant, grains/panicle, % fertile spikelets/panicle,

1,000-grain weight, grain and straw yield, and harvest index were recorded and evaluated by correlation and path analyses.

Yield/plant was significantly and positively correlated with number of tillers (0.36), number of panicles (0.39), straw yield (0.25), and harvest index (0.69). Straw yield was significantly and positively correlated with plant height (0.29), number of tillers (0.30), and grains/panicle (0.20). Grains/panicle and % fertility had positive and significant correlation (0.37). Number of panicles was positively and significantly correlated (0.24) with harvest index, but negatively and significantly correlated with grains/panicle (-0.31), % fertility (-0.31), and 1,000-grain weight (-0.27). Number of tillers was negatively and significantly

correlated with grains/panicle (-0.20), % spikelet fertility (-0.28), and 1,000-grain weight (-0.23). The association of plant height and straw was negative and significant (-0.24), as was plant height and number of panicles (-0.23).

Path analysis showed that panicles/plant had maximum direct and indirect effect on grain yield. Grains/panicle, spikelet fertility, and 1,000 grain weight also had direct effects on yield, but those were counterbalanced by a negative indirect effect of panicles/plant.

Results indicate that breeding to develop high yielding, cold-tolerant rices should emphasize number of panicle-bearing tillers/plant, high grains/panicle, good spikelet fertility, and high harvest index. □

Varietal tolerance for low temperature and influence of planting dates and nitrogen fertilization

K. A. Ayotade and J. A. Akinremi, National Cereals Research Institute, Rice Research Station, Badeggi via Bida, Nigeria

From 1979-81 dry seasons, 463 entries from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were screened for vegetative stage tolerance for 16-20°C temperatures. Seeds were sown 14 Oct and transplanted 15 Nov. Seedlings of each line were planted 2/hill in a 5-m-long plot with 4 rows spaced at 25 × 25 cm. NPK was applied at 120-40-40 kg/ha, with N applied in 3 equal splits.

Ten promising entries were selected

Table 1. Agronomic characters of 10 outstanding entries selected from 463 entries in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery; 1979-81 dry season (Nov-Mar)^a Badeggi, Nigeria.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Spikelet fertility	Panicle exertion	Phenotypic acceptability
RPKN-2	4.4	115	118	X	X	X
B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3	5.6	121	122	X	X	X
KULU	4.8	121	119	X	X	X
KN-361-BKK-27-1	4.4	115	118	X	X	X
IR9202-36-3-2	6.0	139	100	X	X	X
B737F-KN-10-3-1-2	5.6	118	120	X	X	X
IR9202-25-1-3	7.2	120	108	X	X	X
IR8965-K1	6.0	122	77	X	X	X
IR9224-K1	6.0	106	94	X	X	X
IR9202-22-3-2	6.8	139	99	X	X	X

^ax = promising entries.

(Table 1) for further field evaluation on the basis of plant height, growth duration, tiller number, leaf color, panicle emergence, flowering uniformity, spikelet

sterility, phenotypic acceptability, grain size, and grain yield.

The 1982 performance of the entries was evaluated at three planting dates and